

Biocul tural

**Biocultural diversity for the
conservation of rural areas**

diver sity

BIOCULTURAL LANDSCAPES
EXPERIENCES FROM SOUTHEAST SPAIN

SCALABLE project

This project has received funding from the **European Union's Horizon 2020** research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101031168.

The main objective is to identify pathways to conserve biocultural diversity in rural areas of Southern Spain. The specific objectives are:

- 1/ IDENTIFY** the practices and elements of biocultural diversity that are in rural areas.
- 2/ ANALYZE AND MAP** the elements of biocultural diversity.
- 3/ EVALUATE** how rural areas provide human-nature connection and human well-being.
- 4/ DEFINE FUTURE STRATEGIES** to maintain local well-being and conserve biocultural landscapes.

THANKS

We are deeply grateful to the local communities, as well as the local and regional authorities of the region, without whose collaboration and enthusiasm our work would not be possible.

Study sites:

Rural areas of the southeast of Spain linked to traditional agriculture.

Three rural municipalities were chosen, which face depopulation and rural abandonment. All of them are small municipalities (< 2000 inhabitants) that have traditionally had traditional agriculture that is now being lost, and **where the relationship between nature and culture is deep**:

Almócita
(Alpujarra's Almería)

Purchena
(Almanzora's region)

Abrucena
(Nacimiento's River)

What is rural abandonment and why we should care about it

Rural abandonment refers to the process by which people and economic activities move from rural to urban areas, leaving traditional farmlands without management.

Some basic data

470.000 km²
RURAL AREAS IN SPAIN

OF THE SURFACE AREA IN SPAIN

OF MUNICIPALITIES IN SPAIN HAVE LOST THEIR POPULATION

24%

RURAL POPULATION

Large disproportion in the distribution of the territory

76%

URBAN POPULATION

Migration to cities due to lack of economic opportunities, jobs, basic services and infrastructure.

Rural abandonment can represent opportunities for renaturalization, but also problems for local communities:

Economic: it can lead to a decrease in agricultural production, which would negatively affect the local and national economy and food security.

Sociocultural: contributes to the depopulation of rural areas, which has a negative impact on culture, knowledge, and traditions, with important impact on the quality of life of local communities.

Ecological: can cause soil degradation and biodiversity loss, negatively affecting the environment and sustainability.

Rural areas as a refugia for the conservation of biocultural diversity

Some rural areas may represent areas with high levels of biodiversity and also cultural diversity, exemplifying sustainable management of the territory. **Biocultural diversity highlights the links that exist between biological, linguistic and cultural diversities.**

It recognizes that the interaction between nature and local populations can generate high values of biodiversity and high values of cultural diversity, promoting sustainable systems.

Human-nature connectedness in rural areas

Rural abandonment and depopulation towards urban areas is causing the disconnection between people and nature and could aggravate the environmental crisis.

CASE OF STUDY OF PURCHENA

Local population feels highly connected to nature

Local people value living in a rural environment due to the connections and interactions they have with nature. The place holds significance for them: they feel connected through their experiences in nature and they feel like a part of it.

Type of nature's value:

Why live in a rural area?

Local population would recommend living in a rural environment, because it provides **multitude of components of human well-being**.

How to stop rural abandonment and promote rural development?

CASE STUDY OF ALMÓCITA

In recent years, Almócita has become a proactive municipality, in which its inhabitants and the local government work cooperatively to promote projects and activities aimed at sustainable development, with the aim of attracting and establishing a population.

Improving good quality of life in Almócita

They strengthen local trade and production of fresh foods, which preserves the landscape and fosters a connection with nature.

They facilitate the flow of knowledge and strengthen the sense of a small community.

Participation in the activities generates tranquility, increases relationships among neighbors, and promotes the local economy.

Some activities preserve traditions and, therefore, protect cultural heritage.

Research team

The research team has been formed by researchers from the University of Almería.

Dra. Cristina Quintas Soriano, Principal investigator of SCALABLE project

Dr. Antonio J. Castro, Coordinator of SCALABLE project

Carmen López Zayas, researcher and coordinator of fieldwork in Purchena

Caterina Recalde, researcher and coordinator of fieldwork in Almócita

Ana Isabel Latorre Andrés, researcher and coordinator of fieldwork in Abrucena

Dra. María López Rodríguez, co-advisor of the research work in Abrucena

Dr. Juan Miguel Requena Mullor, co-advisor of the research work in Almócita

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Contact: Cristina Quintas Soriano /cqs572@ual.es
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